
MULTIDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION: A REPORT ON THE MONITORING EXPERIENCE IN THE ONE HEALTH CURRICULAR COMPONENT

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Introduction: Tutoring is an educational tool that encourages students to develop integrated learning in teaching, research, and extension activities in undergraduate courses. This pedagogical modality allows the tutor to immerse themselves in teaching and learning practices, offering benefits to all involved. It is an opportunity for students to develop fundamental skills for teaching practice. Tutoring also promotes academic engagement among those being tutored by reducing anxiety and the impact associated with the transition to higher education.

Objective: To expand the exposure experienced in tutoring for the One Health curricular component offered by the Federal University of Southern Bahia, highlighting the importance of inclusive practices in the academic environment. **Case report/experience:** To implement the tutoring project, four hours per week were allocated to online meetings with students enrolled in the component, seeking to answer questions and guide the steps of reading, interpretation, and scientific writing. Some of these meetings were supervised by the professor, in order to model the tutoring activity. In addition, frequent meetings were held between the monitors and the teachers, linked to the discussion of aspects related to the teaching methods applied in the curricular component. During the monitoring period, one student had autism spectrum disorder, requiring more participatory monitoring. To meet this demand, pedagogical strategies were

applied that favored her inclusion, such as reinforcing explanations, making the teaching approach more flexible, and encouraging constant dialogue. As a result of all the activities carried out by the monitors, content was created on Instagram with the topics covered in the CC, aiming to spread the discussions that took place in the classroom to the entire external community on social networks. At the end of the school year, the monitors directly assisted in the organization and production of the last assessment activity in the form of a seminar, and in the writing of the final CC report by the students. This experience provided the monitors with an immersion in inclusive teaching practices, allowing a broader understanding of the needs of the students and the role of monitoring in promoting an academic environment accessible to all.

Conclusion: The tutoring offered an improvement in the critical spirit regarding the strengths and weaknesses of a scientific text and the interest in the academic field. In addition, the interaction with a student with autism reinforced the importance of inclusive pedagogical practices, highlighting the need for adaptations to meet different profiles. This experience promoted more learning and improvement for all involved, consolidating the tutoring as a space for academic training and social inclusion.

Keywords: Education; Teaching; Inclusion; Pedagogical practices.